

Funded by
the European Union

POST-EVENT REPORT

COMPETENCE CENTRES FOR SEMICONDUCTORS

Considerations from Users

April 2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgements	3
Disclaimer	3
Introduction	5
Executive Summary	6
Most immediate needs	7
Services offered by competence centres	8
Perspectives from SMEs	9
SME Recommendations	9
Perspectives from Large Industry	10
Large Industry Recommendations	10
Perspectives from Trade Associations and Clusters	11
Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations	11
Perspectives from Research	12
Research Recommendations	12
Perspectives from National Authorities & Policy	13
National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations	13
Specialisations of competence centres	14
Perspectives from SMEs	15
SME Recommendations	15
Perspectives from Large Industry	16
Large Industry Recommendations	16
Perspectives from Trade Associations and Clusters	17
Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations	17
Perspectives from Research	18
Research Recommendations	18
Perspectives from National Authorities & Policy	19
National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations	19
Conditions for services offered	20
Perspectives from SMEs	21
SME Recommendations	21
Perspectives from Large Industry	22
Large Industry Recommendations	22
Perspectives from Trade Associations and Clusters	23
Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations	23
Perspectives from Research	24
Research Recommendations	24
Perspectives from National Authorities & Policy	25
National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations	25
Conclusions	27
Annex: Snapshots from the Live Brainstorming Sessions	28

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Representative from the following organisations were invited to the Workshop:

AENEAS, AMD, Arm France, ASM, Brainport Eindhoven, CEA-Leti, CITC, Cluster Semiconductors, CoE Talent Acquisition, Digital Innovation Zone EDIH, Dispelix, ELINCLUS, EPoSS, EUROPOLARIS, Excillum AB, Flanders Semiconductors, Free Silicon Foundation, Fundación Instituto Ricardo Valle de Innovación INNOVA IRV, GARR, High Tech NL, IMEC, Infineon Technologies, Inside Industry Association, Institute of Microelectronics of Barcelona, Intel Corporation, IPC, Logicdev EU, Malta Enterprise, Ministerul Economiei, NXP, Oost NL, OpenForum Europe, Permanent Representation of Romania to the EU, Research Council of Norway, Samman, Samsung, Siemens, Silicon Austria Lab, Silicon Saxony, SINTEF, SPEA, Stiftung Neue Verantwortung, STMicroelectronics, THALES, Thermo Fisher Scientific, TNO, Tyndall National Institute, VTT, Warsaw University of Technology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, X-FAB Semiconductor Foundries, YbotX

The event was organised and this report was produced by ALLPROS.eu: Silvana Muscella, Lottie Boas, Rob Carrillo, Davide Casarin, Valeriya Fetisova, Paula Grzegorzewska, Nuria de Lama, Richard Stevens, and Helena Winigerm, with the support of KDT JU the European institution that runs the European programme that will implement the Competence Centres: Yves Gigase, Huascar Espinoza, Eric Fribourg-Blanc, Francisco Ignacio, Georgi Kuzmanov, and Anne Salaun, under the guidance of the European Commission DG CONNECT Microelectronics and Photonics Industry Unit representatives Arian Zwegers, Thomas Reibe, Matthew Xuereb, and Stefano Selleri.

DISCLAIMER

The information and views set out in this document are those of the authors and speakers invited to the workshop and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Nor does the European Commission guarantee the accuracy of the information included in this report. Neither the European Commission, nor any person acting on the European Commission's behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

INTRODUCTION

Many would be surprised to learn that microchips are the new oil - the scarce resource on which the modern world depends. Today, military, economic, and geopolitical power are built on a foundation of computer chips. Virtually everything - from missiles to microwaves, smartphones to the stock market - runs on semiconductors. Today, the modern semiconductor landscape is where advanced chips are constructed from the smallest electronic components ever manufactured to support an industry that is gargantuan in scale and involves massively complex, globalised supply chains serving some of the world's most valuable companies¹.

To overcome **barriers** in the field of semiconductors and chips, a PEST analysis with barriers is described herein to articulate some of the issues that need addressing within the Competence Centres, and which were also touched upon by the participants at the workshop. Firstly, the following **Political Factors** have to be addressed: **Current limitations in Europe on workforce skills** are forcing Europe to consider effective Mobility Programmes and stronger synergies between governments, academia and industry to provide skills in this domain. **National and European regulations hinder innovation** - this is where projects and initiatives in Europe must look at mapping European strengths, to help fast-track permit granting procedures. There is a need for **transparency** whilst protecting confidential information of companies - mapping exercises and the introduction of open models can certainly help in this regard. The **need to reduce dependencies** on a small number of suppliers outside of the EU is important, and to concentrate on an entire ecosystem to avoid single points of failure is key.

To overcome barriers related to **Social Factors**, today there is lack of control among the citizens, private sector and public sector **due to overreliance on technologies from few organisations**. Therefore, a more geopolitically balanced production of chips is paramount in making Europe stronger and more secure. Concerns over citizen's security due to the war in Ukraine have added to the urgency of ensuring the security of the EU, by broadening the chip supplier base and diversifying supply chains to manage risk. Disruptions in the consumer goods supply chain have led to delays in the delivery of everyday goods (e.g., cars, domestic utilities, etc.).

What was not discussed in detail but may be considered for further consideration are the boundary conditions of the Competence Centres to already existing infrastructures such as the local Innovation hubs, or the local semiconductor industry associations. The innovation angle for patent filing and exploitation, the Standardisation efforts (both European & international, IEC TC47, Trusted secure chips, etc) and public procurement, which could drive the demand side for such chips, through their design, production equipment & facilities etc.

To overcome barriers related to Economic Factors, there is a need to attract talent to create an "EU talent pool" for semiconductor-related jobs. In order to bridge the gap to the new skill sets required in the semiconductor supply chain - from technicians to engineers - there is a need both to strengthen the university curricula and to provide opportunities for upskilling individuals who have lost their jobs due to recent waves of lay-offs.

To overcome barriers related to Technological Factors, there is a need to avoid interruptions in the semiconductor supply chain by introducing cross-fertilisation programmes, outreach, and international joint events between the EU and global initiatives. Finally, there is a lack of standardisation in the chips-related industry and immaturity in the process of certification of chips. Certification of trusted, secure, and green chips should be based on market-driven international standards. The implementation of the Chips Act², where a provisional political agreement was reached on the regulation to strengthen Europe's semiconductor ecosystem on the same day of this workshop, is seen as a major step in addressing Europe's weaknesses in semiconductors and reinforces its place in a global and interdependent ecosystem.

1. "Chip War - the fight for the world's most critical technology" - Author:Chris Miller, Publisher Scribner

2. "Chips Act: Council and European Parliament strike provisional deal"

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/04/18/chips-act-council-and-european-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The interactive workshop on **competence centres for semiconductors**, organised online on the 18th April 2023 in collaboration with the European Commission DG Connect and the KDT JU, gathered together over 100 registrants. It was designed to bring together **industry stakeholders, including startups, SMEs, and mid-caps, industry experts and researchers** who are interested in the latest developments on how competence centres should be structured to support the ever-growing industry of semiconductors. Specifically, the event was an opportunity to discuss **how competence centres in semiconductors can serve the needs of industrial stakeholders**.

The workshop addresses the first pillar of the **Chips Act - the Chips for Europe Initiative** that reinforces **Europe's technological leadership**, by facilitating the transfer of knowledge from the lab to the fab, bridging the gap between research and innovation and industrial activities and promoting the industrialisation of innovative technologies by European businesses.

Moreover the workshop featured introductory speeches by the European Commission and a series of practical, hands-on breakout sessions where stakeholders were put into the driving seat to express their expectations for Competence Centres through a set of guided questions to answer that are elaborated in detail in the subsequent sections of this report. Breakout sessions included topics on considerations for: (1) services offered by the competence centres, (2) specialisations of competence centres, and (3) conditions for services offered.

3. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-chips-act-communication-regulation-joint-undertaking-and-recommendation>

MOST IMMEDIATE NEEDS

Kicking off the workshop, organisations were asked to indicate some of their most immediate needs in the context of semiconductor industry competence centres.

The audience, which comprised SMEs, large enterprises, trade associations, innovation clusters, research initiatives, and policy actors, cited a few priorities, most of them revolving around talent acquisition and addressing the existing skills gap, knowledge sharing, obtaining technical and operational support as well as specific policy directions and ecosystem development.

Specifically on **talent acquisition and addressing the skills gap**, overall, there was general agreement on the need to attract and engage graduate talent. Other points from the participants included having a skills assessment framework and mapping to upcoming workloads, certifying competencies and procedures, and addressing how to improve talent retention.

Better knowledge sharing or building within the industry was also highlighted. A few of these cited include better knowledge on green technologies and legacy and getting knowhow on designing and building heterogeneous systems.

Another significant challenge area which saw many contributions from participants is having **improved technical and operational capacities**. Among these include an easily accessible database of consolidated chip VHDL/layout IP blocks (i.e, open-source), dedicated production facilities and process development for more than Moore chips, advanced packaging solutions, having better connections between equipment manufacturers with end users or fabs, implementing a quality assurance framework, support for blue sky research and innovation, and training personnel for SMEs. There was also a more technical point on improving the open source Yosys software (used in hardware design) to generate better error messages.

On **policy directions and development of the semiconductors ecosystem**, there was a strong call for transparency and ensuring representation of stakeholders. These include giving SMEs a voice in consultation bodies, having a working Alliance on Processors and Semiconductor Technologies or having a reliable and known body on the EU level that represents the voice of the European semiconductors industry in European policy making. Another suggestion was to have a permanent industrial seat in the European Semiconductor Board and transparency on their members and meetings.

A few recommendations were also seen on the role of clusters and existing networks. One point was the need for more understanding on the relation of the planned competence centres compared to existing European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH), European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC), European Digital Infrastructure Consortia (EDIC), and European Chips Infrastructure Consortia (ECIC). Another suggestion was to also consider the use of existing clusters and networks in the field such as Silicon Eurocluster and EDIH.

There was also a call for more manufacturing of diffraction optics in Europe (IC-nanopatterning processes) and further standardisation in the industry.

SERVICES OFFERED BY COMPETENCE CENTRES

The competence centres are an integral part of the Chips Act's approach to the current European semiconductor context, as part of the first pillar in Chips for Europe, which is focused on providing direct support to infrastructure building, SMEs, and start-ups. The challenge being tackled by the initiative is to understand and respond to the current difficulties and missing resources affecting the user-end of the competence centres. Due to the importance of balancing the users' demands with the centres' supplies, workshop attendees were asked to provide input on the main difficulties and needs of their organisation.

Q1 What are the current challenges your organisation is facing for which you would like the support from Competence Centres?

Topic I – Services offered by competence centres

2. **Specific activities:** specific to each national competence centre according to its area of expertise / specialisation

For example:

- Providing scientific/technical expertise/consulting on its specialisation (also to other competence centres)
- Organising events on their areas of expertise

Q2 What types of services would you like to have from the Competence Centres?

Topic I – Services offered by competence centres

1. **General activities:** common to all national competence centres

For example:

- Facilitating access to pilot lines
- Facilitating access to design platform
- Training and skills
- Supporting interested stakeholders in developing semiconductor solutions (technology transfer)
- Matching user needs with available expertise in CC network
- Awareness raising, promoting services, promoting success stories

PERSPECTIVES FROM **SMEs**

With the increasing need to strengthen the semiconductor ecosystem in the EU, a particular focus falls on the European SMEs as cornerstones of the European economy and drivers of digitalisation and regional stability.

As highlighted by the outcomes of the workshop, SMEs and start-ups necessitate significant support to thrive and innovate across the semiconductor field. The challenges they currently face range from limited access to manufacturing facilities to the lack of networking opportunities.

Representing the **12%** of the total participants, the SMEs involved in the workshop highlighted the following challenges:

- Lack of expertise and resources to acquire knowledge in other fields related to the SME's work, such as legal, business coaching, IPR, new technologies consultancy.
- Inaccessible advanced training on specific IC-manufacturing skills and practices. For instance, "know-how" is common for large enterprises, but there are numerous barriers to access it for SMEs.
- Difficulty to establish a network with other businesses on local, regional, and European level, which limits clustering and business opportunities.
- Limited access to design and simulation software, such as advanced EDA tools.
- Insufficient financial support and inaccessible loans and grants. In particular, SMEs experience difficulties in managing resources vs investment at the initial stage.
- Insufficient opportunities to find suppliers for specific IC-processes and network with the whole value chain.
- Limited access to manufacture foundries where pilot manufacturing is available for SMEs.

SME Recommendations

• **Consultation services in business coaching and legal domain**

The consultation services could grant facilitated access to experts in such areas as legal compliance and business development. Furthermore, considering that a business plan is a sensitive aspect for each SME, the participants highlighted the need to receive assistance with creating business plans and conducting market studies. This would reduce the obstacles related to limited resources often faced by SMEs.

• **Capacity building services**

SMEs highlighted the importance of capacity building services, which should include integrated circuits cleanroom services and access to manufacturing equipment considering the high demand for these.

• **Networking opportunities with other stakeholders**

A specific need relates to connecting with universities and leading authorities in the field to exchange knowledge and establish collaboration to incentivise training and attract talent to SMEs.

• **Dissemination of latest research and data**

With limited resources, SMEs find it difficult to access the latest research and market data in the semiconductor industry.

• **Programmes targeted at attracting talent to SMEs**

A common concern for multiple SMEs is the talent shortage and the competition for talent with large enterprises.

To efficiently implement these recommendations, it should be also considered that there are already some existing networks that can be expanded or supported such as the case of the ecosystem of VTT, Aalto University and companies supported by national funding.

PERSPECTIVES FROM **LARGE** **INDUSTRY**

Despite the considerable size of the group of large companies participating in the workshop, there was good convergence about challenges companies are currently facing.

One of the most repeated problems is the lack or **shortage of skills** and this covers multiple dimensions such as the difficulty to hire skilled people or the challenge of retaining existing talent (i.e. avoiding that employees move to other organizations looking for better conditions). In fact, a problem in the origin consisting of the lack of vocation was also highlighted. This shows that actions may be needed at different stages of the educational and training processes. This also relates to inclusiveness (e.g. engagement of women) and a more efficient way to deliver training (e.g. by sharing capacities and facilities) that could lead to better results.

- Access to different stakeholders and generally speaking, creating a rich **ecosystem where different players collaborate in a seamless way** taking advantage of each others' capacities for the benefit of the different actors is also a major challenge that expands technical concepts and involves organisational and legal aspects. In this context we can point out concrete aspects such as facilitating access to RTOs and joint research between several institutions, but also suitable connection and collaboration with design startups.
- The third category of challenges addresses technical and infrastructure components. A good example of a very concrete challenge is access to pilot lines.

Large Industry Recommendations

- **Services for knowledge sharing**
Without entering in details about how opportunities or knowledge should be shaped, participants were, however, concerned about the complexity to access knowledge from the different competence centers. In this context, there seems to be consensus around the fact that easy-to-use interfaces should be created and companies should not waste time in checking what each CC can offer and jump from one to another until they find what they need. A kind-of one-stop-shop should be available to simplify operations.
- **Services aimed at the access and development of skills**
As mentioned above, this could involve a range of functionalities, such as: access to training facilities, the provision of education services as such for development of skills in different disciplines but also for different audiences or levels (e.g. bachelor, masters level), access to top-level teachers or the set-up of a credentials/micro-credentials framework, to name a few.
- Optic design and optical component prototyping was one of the technical aspects highlighted in the discussion, but others like AI for chip manufacturing were also raised.
- Guidance on **IP management** is a very concrete element of the service package companies would like to have. In this context, application engineering support on IP and EDA tools was also mentioned.

PERSPECTIVES FROM TRADE ASSOCIATIONS AND CLUSTERS

This group consisted of trade associations and clusters, which made the feedback received more specific to the group as they would not be directly the target group of the competence centers, but rather could act on behalf of the members of their organisations thus a consultation process is needed as well. It was an argument repeated by the participants of this group that there are several initiatives within clusters, associations and others that are doing the work that competence centres should learn from and build on their expertise.

The challenges that the group identified were:

- There is a need to map and use the existing analysis, processes and collaboration schemes, for example in Silicon Saxony, that is willing to share the experience with other regions where competence centers (or clusters) are going to be set up.
- Providing support for expertise and skills on ECS along the entire value chain
- A network of competence centers should have transparent info on all running projects and initiatives on EU level, including KDT JU projects, Erasmus+, DEP projects, etc
- There is a need of interesting more students in semiconductor related studies
- Access to specific training on the topic is a challenge, as many topics are fairly niche and training is often available only in particular parts of the world/Europe
- Access to funding for operationalising the Competence Center
- The participants were unsure of the agreed upon definition of a “competence center” and expressed that there should be a definition of its role, competencies and goals for the industry to be able to benefit from its existence
- Uncertainty about the role of the European Digital Innovation Hubs

Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations

- **“Test before invest” services for SMEs**
These would be very helpful, allowing for minimising the need for investments and lowering the barrier of entry.
- **Building more large industry and startups partnerships**
Corporate and startups partnership matchmaking can help increase the innovativeness of the European semiconductor industry and based on schemes that have been used in many other industries.
- **Professional reskilling**
Dependent on the needs.
- **Collaboration**
Establish more collaborations with existing initiatives, such as the Silicon Europe Alliance

PERSPECTIVES FROM **RESEARCH**

This group consisted of participants from Universities, and RTOs. Their point of view with regards to the Competence Centers should take into account the fact that they would likely be on the supply side of the services offered to the industry players. While the questions were designed for the consultation of organisations demanding the services offered by the CCs, the role of these stakeholders remains of key importance in the planning process for the network. Participants noted that offering training on cutting edge research fields overlaps with activities carried out within academia. It was argued that the relationship between the CCs and academia itself should be taken into consideration during the design of the CC network.

More specifically, the main challenges highlighted by the participants in this group were the following:

- Lack of access to good quality IP regarding the specific / individual steps of chip design.
- Lack of access to production information especially from the perspective of RTOs
- Lack of access to open-source design tools, combined with lack of funding
- Difficulties in finding trained personnel
- Lack of alignment with similar initiatives at EU level and the consequent duplication of efforts
- Lack of definition of a quality assurance and certification framework
- Difficulties connecting with professionals working within the same areas of interests and beyond

Research Recommendations

- Access to training. The range of training spans from generic to specialized (including hands-on brief and practical programmes)
- Consultancy services
- Access to EDA tools and Process Design Kits
- Pre pilot line prototyping / design prototyping within the competence centers to then allow companies to move on to the next stages of pilot lines development.
- Provide technology transfer and core knowledge necessary to innovate to fill the lack of known best practices and methodologies
- Educate about express certification procedures, especially using open-source hardware standards

PERSPECTIVES FROM NATIONAL AUTHORITIES & POLICY⁴

The main challenges public bodies are facing for which they believe competence centres could support are in the areas of being able to support local industry to identify potential partners and hireable individuals with the technical and engineering competencies and business skills needed to integrate the various technologies that intersect in chip engineering, packaging, production and introduction into industrial processes.

In particular, in education and training, as well as access to detailed technical information and consulting.

National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations

- **Training and point of reference**

Ensure competence centres provide users with training and technical information regarding where to find consultants with design knowhow for heterogeneous system integration especially knowhow for combining different types of chips (IC, RF, microfluidic, photonics etc).

- **Take into account country sizes and specificities**

Ensure there is good logic and reasoning for developing competence centres in smaller countries that might not have a flourishing microprocessor industry or manufacturing industry adopting or implementing technologies.

- **Cross-border knowledge sharing**

Ensure there is broad access and sharing of knowledge across Europe and ensure that competence centres have access to pan-European knowledge for designing complex heterogeneous systems.

4. The views expressed here from the National Authorities provide only a small sample set of considerations that are not representative of the entire EU national authorities' opinions.

SPECIALISATIONS OF COMPETENCE CENTRES

As the purpose of the competence centres is to provide high-quality training and knowledge to users, there is the matter of deciding what kind of information should be provided and whether or not different competence centres should specialise in different areas of the field, or perhaps the competence centre system as a whole should pursue a limited number of specialisations. In the interest of gauging the user-end's interest and need for such specialisations, workshop attendees were asked to provide their thoughts on specialisation preferences and training models.

Q1 Which specialisation area do you think is a priority at this point in time (hardware, software, design, manufacturing etc.)

Q2 What is the best model for training in the specialisation area that you think Competence Centres should adopt?

Topic II – Specialisation of competence centres

- Can you think of general or specific functions or activities for competence centres beyond the ones mentioned above?
- How can competence centres leverage already ongoing initiatives to realise specialised European hubs of excellence?
- Can you foresee which specific activities or specialisation a national competence centre could focus on?
- What should competence centres do to increase/stimulate European activities in design?

PERSPECTIVES FROM **SMEs**

Based on the needs and challenges related to the limited resources experienced by the SMEs, the preferred areas of specialization majorly focus on the provision of support in accessing simulation tools, manufacturing facilities, and labs that are often unaffordable for SMEs.

More specifically, the participants representing SMEs highlighted the following priorities for Competence Centres specializations:

- Provision of prototype for evaluation, testing capacities, and access to labs. Specialization on metrology and manufacturing hardware (CVD/PVD, patterning, pilot or manufacturing with open access).
- Support related to accessing EDA simulation tools. To facilitate access to it, some participants suggested an hourly based model.
- Guarantee of open access to manufacturing capacities for start-ups and SMEs.
- Creation of a pool of expertise and available consultants that can provide support to SMEs.

SME Recommendations

Recruitment of highly qualified personnel for SMEs operating in the semiconductor industry is particularly challenging as there is high competition with large enterprises and a lack of available external training resources. Overall, SMEs often rely on in-house training as the only viable option to train employees on new processes, such as optics or quantum computing. Nevertheless, because of the limited exchange of know-how, SMEs struggle to capitalise the internal knowledge and require additional support in training.

Some of the suggested training models include:

- **Alternation model**
This partners universities specifically to SMEs from an early stage of the students' curricula. With such a model, students would acquire in-demand skills in companies on a weekly basis, which would facilitate the future employment of recent graduates and establish a pool of trained young professionals that SMEs could employ.
- **Cluster model**
This connects SMEs from a specific region through the competence centres. With shared training on a regional basis, SMEs could exchange knowledge and establish long-term cooperation focused on the best practices.
- **Online training**
This can be carried out through targeted webinars to update professionals on a specific subject, particularly on new technologies.
- **Crash courses**
These can range between three and six months and are coupled with internship and on-hand training for further skills development.
- **Exchange working opportunities**
This is done between niche professionals within a region. By creating a pool of such professionals, the Competence Centre could facilitate short-term employment opportunities within SMEs.
- **Mentoring programmes**
These identify senior professionals and connect them with young professionals that just graduated or entered the industry.

PERSPECTIVES FROM **LARGE** **INDUSTRY**

There was a big variety of answers with respect to specialization, where the following areas were pointed out:

- Classic optics design/mechatronics/material science
- Chip design, verification and HW implementation. RISC-V processors (open source) for strategic EU domains like automotive, industrial, ultra low power IoT were also mentioned
- Advanced packaging and back-end manufacturing
- System design and rapid prototyping, addressing both SW and HW
- Collaborative venturing, support for SMEs and for startups to raise public funding but also in areas like IP licensing
- Metrology and test, including test engineering, materials and device characterization and analysis, power instrumentation design for test equipment
- Chip manufacturing including lithography and AI support

Large Industry Recommendations

Going beyond the nature of the contents (the “what”) to the way they could be instrumentalised (the “how”), multiple ideas emerged from the discussion about potential training models to be used by the competence centres. This includes:

- **On-job training, apprenticeships but also hybrid training models** should be considered.
- Access to real-life **training facilities**.
- **Cooperation** with companies, internships, PhDs; establishment of public-private partnerships. This collaboration between different institutions is a way forward to take advantage of experts and top content. For example, collaboration with universities is sought, where companies could benefit from dedicated courses organised by universities in specific domains.
- **EDA tools** and **PDK training**
- Provide **sandbox environments**
- Training on **chip design** (Arm.based, soc, multiphysics)

Looking at a European environment where companies could make use of services provided by CCs in other Member States (MS), a degree of standardisation would be needed along the range of services. This also applies to training models, where some work may be needed to make compatible curricula from different MS.

Some companies see the framework of Innovation projects as a nurturing environment for training purposes and as such they would like to see CC supporting the set-up of EU projects as a way to bring together different stakeholders in the value chain, including big companies and startups.

PERSPECTIVES FROM **TRADE ASSOCIATIONS AND CLUSTERS**

The group has a wide range of members, partners and contacts within the industry, thus several specialisation areas were selected.

Those include:

- Design Small series production of wafers
- Design and prototyping support
- Embedded software
- Edge AI (both HW and SW technologies)
- System of systems engineering
- Engineering process for design, develop, test, validation
- Materials knowledge (SiN, GaN etc)
- Packaging capacity
- Low threshold access
- Equipment for heterogeneous integration power electronics heterogeneous integration design for low-power

Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations

- **Exchange of personnel**
- Providing opportunities for learning by **temporary placements** in other companies
- **Knowledge exchange** within mutually beneficial ways, on the workplace training.

PERSPECTIVES FROM **RESEARCH**

Participants in Group 4 identified a number of key specialization areas that should be prioritized in the network of competence centers for the semiconductor industry.

These included:

- Hardware, design & manufacturing. Participants noted that the software area is already covered by the resources available through the EDIHs
- Low energy computing
- Advanced packaging technologies with access for SMEs
- Green Electronic Components and Systems technologies, including material research
- Medical applications: heterogeneous systems

This list of priority areas seems to reflect the participants' recognition of a wide range of critical challenges facing the industry, such as energy efficiency, environmental impact, and healthcare.

Research Recommendations

- **Remote training**
- **Connection with cutting edge researchers**
- Provide clear **documentation** of all key knowledge and tools
- Collaboration with already **existing learning centres / academies**
- **Network technologies** to give lecturers an overview of students' progress
- **Chip design courses**

PERSPECTIVES FROM NATIONAL AUTHORITIES & POLICY⁵

Public Authorities have a good idea of the types of services that their potential users (businesses, research centres) in their regions would like to have from the Competence Centres. As per the recommendations described in the same group earlier, the main challenges for training are on design and engineering of complex heterogeneous systems.

National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations

- **Co-development**
The group believed that promoting co-development across different users of the CEs and Across different CEs themselves could lead to more comprehensive trainings.
- **Advanced packaging**
The group wanted to ensure the CEs moved beyond traditional engineering and included advanced packaging solutions needs.
- **Catalogue of services and competencies**
The EU should ensure that there is a coordinated catalogue of services and competencies in the competence centres so that users and organisers know where to turn for the needed expertise.
- **Design support**
Provide access to knowledge and training on Electronic Design Automation (EDA) Software for designing, simulating, and verifying digital circuits to help designers create complex designs, identify potential issues, and optimise performance.
- **Programming languages**
Hardware Description Languages (HDLs) to allow designers to describe digital circuits using code. Examples (Verilog and VHDL).
- **Logic Synthesis Tools**
To take high-level circuit description and generate a lower-level netlist that can be used for physical design to optimise circuit performance, reduce power consumption, and improve timing.
- **Place and Route Tools**
To optimise chip performance, reduce power consumption, and minimise the chip's size.
- **Verification Tools**
to ensure that the digital circuit behaves as intended, and to identify and correct any errors or issues before manufacturing.
- **Disruptive application labs, and test facilities**
For unproven applications.

5. The views expressed here from the National Authorities provide only a small sample set of considerations that are not representative of the entire EU national authorities' opinions.

CONDITIONS FOR SERVICES OFFERED

As a final point of discussion, Mr. Xuereb focused on the topic of interaction: the objective of the competence centres is not only to provide access to information but to incentivize user interaction and growth through targeted support and cooperation. On this front, to address the needs of the users and understand the type of services they may expect from the competence centres, workshop attendees were asked to envision their potential interactions with the centres and highlight the services they would be particularly enthusiastic about.

Q1 How do you see the interaction working between the Competence Centres and your organisation? What would make you and your organisation make use of the competence centre? (some examples could be: to learn how to run a test or scale up your solutions? guarantee a solid network to link different kinds of stakeholders to help pool together expertise? develop joint advocacy work? etc ...)

Topic III – Interaction with Competence Centres

- Which entities should be eligible for free or facilitated access to Competence Centres?
- How can Competence Centres accelerate the path for SMEs to get to prototype? What resources should they provide?
- How should Competence Centres interact with larger enterprises?
- How can larger companies leverage Competence Centres? What collaborations do you foresee?

PERSPECTIVES FROM **SMEs**

Considering that SMEs are often unable to access manufacturing facilities and labs because of bottlenecks and scarce resources, an essential aspect would be the ability to directly contact the Competence Centre, inquire whether it meets the SMEs' requirements in terms of mediation of appropriate capacities, and to obtain access to its direct, associated or mediated services and capacities within a short period of time.

To achieve this, the workshop participants suggested:

- Establishing a scattered model of interaction between SMEs and Competence Centres across Europe to guarantee easy access to the provided services and capacities in the shortest time possible.
- Building an online platform that would allow SMEs to interact with the Competence Centres online, apply for support and monitor the progress they made towards achieving the set objectives.

SME Recommendations

- **Streamlined interactions**
Have a smooth application procedure and Timely response by the Competence Centre
- **Reduce red tape**
Absence of bureaucratic barriers that would disadvantage SMEs in obtaining the needed support.
- **Quality**
Guaranteed quality and availability of services and facilities without delays.
- **Accessible location**
Easily accessible (geographical) location that would enable SMEs to establish a direct contact with the Competence Centre.
- **Funding support**
Assistance in applying for financial support and obtaining a greater understanding of the legal compliance requirements.

PERSPECTIVES FROM **LARGE** **INDUSTRY**

Large companies participating in this exercise were asked to reflect about the ways for them to cooperate with the Competence Centers. Reflections shared in the session included more general considerations about the organisational structure of CC and not only about the relationship with big companies.

- Establishment of strategic partnerships, getting companies as direct stakeholders of the CC with the possibility to sign agreements for particular aspects
- Companies see CC as a potential orchestrator to connect different stakeholders based on supply and demand needs. For example, CC, if built upon an extensive knowledge of startups in the sector, could easily understand what kind of services they would need and redirect to the most suitable providers, maybe after first level support provided by the CC itself. Similarly, CC could be intermediaries to identify a top University working on a topic of utmost priority for a company and put them in touch. In this sense, they should anticipate potential valuable relationships and facilitate those interactions.
- There is a general understanding that CC should consider a combination of public and private investments and this, relationships should reflect such financial efforts in decision-making structures
- Strong interaction with Member States is sought to avoid fragmentation and duplication of work, but also to get a comprehensive picture of strengths and weaknesses of the European semiconductors landscape that can trigger actions of value for European stakeholders. Cooperation should help to create strong assets and anticipate problems, as well as to generate critical mass.
- Access to equipment and infrastructure, as mentioned in previous sessions is given as a clear motivation for CC but will require clear procedures on their use.
- Coordination of training programmes would be beneficial at the level of generation of content, but also timing, efficiency in use of resources and others.

Large Industry Recommendations

- **Enable access**
Access to experts, knowledge and skills is a priority feature.
- **Collaboration, networking, strengthening partnerships**
CCs are seen as key enablers to identify and connect different stakeholders based on needs and priorities. They should have a clear view on all the actors and their capacities and as such, could play an instrumental role in ecosystem building.
- **Enhance the visibility of companies and facilitate business relationships**
Different ways to do this exist, starting with simple ones like the elaboration of success stories to more complex ones.
- **Clarity in offerings**
CC should provide clear services including distribution channels, terms and conditions. They should lead to great simplification in the usage of services instead of generating additional complexities to companies.
- **Avoid fragmentation**
Fragmentation should be avoided by all means (services should help to scale and complement for a more efficient use of resources instead of leading to duplication of efforts).

PERSPECTIVES FROM **TRADE ASSOCIATIONS AND CLUSTERS**

Again, the group put a very strong emphasis on utilising the existing networks, initiatives and programmes throughout the Member States. The participants offered to share a list of production facilities (like 'Yellow Pages' book) with a network of 110+ companies.

- CCs should analyse all previous and existing initiatives already funded not to double the efforts,
- A thorough mapping and the overview of existing services, support efforts etc. should be done,
- CCs should provide information available from other organisations and initiatives, fulfilling a role of an information hub,
- CCs could act as one-stop-shops directing companies and organisations towards more specialised services, funding and networks

Trade Associations and Clusters Recommendations

- **Take into account country specificities**
Diverse organisation models that could be taken up, dependent on the country, budgets and cross-border coordination of CCs.
- **Utilise existing networks and resources**
Have a great understanding of the semiconductor industry in the EU in order to use existing resources and 'connect the dots' - companies with services that they need and networks that could be beneficial.
- **Matchmaking**
Matchmaking and providing contacts for services requested by companies.
- **Landscape mapping**
Thorough mapping of all all existing semiconductor EU initiatives, regularly updated and carried out in relation with diverse stakeholders.
- **Point of reference for collaborations**
Using the CCs to connect with all other initiatives to truly connect the players all over Europe.
- **Training**
Lead to efficient personnel training in specific techniques.

PERSPECTIVES FROM RESEARCH

From the discussion about the modes of interaction with the Competence Centers it emerged that representatives of the Research group envisage on one hand a more open, free approach and on another hand a membership based interaction as possible models.

In fact, the responses provided included:

- Membership structure granting access to resources
- Interaction through appointed representatives from the RTOs and academia
- Open access & transparency
- Combination of virtual and physical services

As mentioned, the perspective of the participants contributing to the discussion in group 4 was on what will be the supply side of the services within the framework of the Competence Centers. With regards to this an interesting point was made on the the possibility of appointing representatives of the RTOs involved in the competence centers managing the interaction with the organization demanding the services.

Research Recommendations

- **Development support**
Low cost / free access to tech development.
- **EU-projects collaborations**
Networking opportunities for collaboration on EU projects.
- **Training**
Opportunity to receive training.
- **Avoid redundancy**
Avoid overlapping products and services.
- **Stronger policy links**
Engagement opportunities with policy makers.

Overall these reflect the diverse needs of research-related stakeholders in the industry, ranging from the practical concerns of accessing resources and avoiding duplication of efforts, to the more strategic goals of building networks and engaging with policy makers. As research-related stakeholders play a critical role in supplying the services necessary for the competence centres, their input on how to engage with the centres and make use of their resources is essential in ensuring the success of the network.

PERSPECTIVES FROM NATIONAL AUTHORITIES & POLICY⁶

To the question how do you see the interaction working between the Competence Centres and your organisations, the response was clear as the respondents in this area were from ministries and public research centres so the interaction will support the core mandate of these organisations and is seen as wholly integrated.

National Authorities & Policy Actors Recommendations

Competence centres should provide a range of services to support the development, design, and manufacturing of microprocessor chips. This should include:

- **Interaction Support**
The competence centre should provide a networking function to allow members in a local microprocessor ecosystem to understand who are and interact with the local community and identify competencies and consultancies.
- **Design Support**
Together with local educational facilities, the centre should provide design support services to help chip designers to optimise their designs, identify and mitigate potential issues, and ensure that their designs meet the required specifications.
- **Technology Evaluation**
The centre should evaluate new and emerging technologies and provide guidance on their suitability for specific applications.
- **Process Development**
The centre should provide process development services to help chip manufacturers to optimise their manufacturing processes and improve their yield and quality.
- **Test and Characterisation**
The centre should provide test and characterisation services to help chip manufacturers to validate their designs and ensure that their chips meet the required performance and reliability standards.
- **Training and Education**
The centre should provide training and education services to help chip designers and manufacturers to stay up-to-date with the latest technologies, trends, and best practices in microprocessor chip manufacturing.
- **Collaborative Research**
The centre should facilitate collaborative research projects between chip designers, manufacturers, and academic institutions, in order to drive innovation and advance the state of the art in microprocessor chip manufacturing.

6. The views expressed here from the National Authorities provide only a small sample set of considerations that are not representative of the entire EU national authorities' opinions.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the discussions, SMEs, Clusters and trade associations, research organisations, National Authorities & Policy Actors and other stakeholders in the electronics industry face **several complex and multifaceted challenges**. These challenges include limited access to manufacturing facilities, insufficient financial support, limited networking opportunities, insufficient access to design and simulation software, and lack of access to quality IP regarding the specific/individual steps of chip design.

To address these challenges, the **Competence Centres should provide a wide range of services**, including business coaching, regulatory compliance, advice on new technologies, networking opportunities, access to prototypes for evaluation, testing capabilities, access to laboratories, and specialisation in metrology and manufacturing hardware. They should also provide support for access to EDA simulation tools and Process Design Kits, free access to manufacturing capacity, and training and technical information to support local industries in identifying potential partners and skilled individuals. These elements are key to promote cross-border knowledge sharing and ensure access to pan-European knowledge.

Areas of specialisation prioritised by participants include design, hardware, software, manufacturing, energy-efficient computing, advanced packaging technologies, environmentally friendly electronic components and system technologies, medical applications, and others. Competence centres should provide networking functions to facilitate interaction within the local microprocessor ecosystem and develop their specialisations accordingly, even in smaller countries with less-developed industries.

Regarding **training models**, participants suggested a dispersed interaction model, building an online platform for easy application and progress monitoring, smooth application procedures, timely response from the competence centre, absence of bureaucratic barriers, guaranteed quality and availability of services, easily accessible location, assistance in applying for financial support, and better understanding of regulatory requirements.

Overall, the competence centres should act as information hubs, provide access to resources, interact through designated representatives of RTOs and academia to facilitate collaborative research projects, provide open access and transparency, and provide a combination of virtual and physical services to industry stakeholders. This includes evaluation of new technologies, process development services, test and characterization services, and training and education services to ensure reskilling and upskilling of chip designers and manufacturers.

Continuing the discussion remains key to the success of competence centres for semiconductors: the challenges facing industry players continue to evolve and require a comprehensive and collaborative approach. The Competence Centres must stay abreast of the latest developments in the industry and be flexible enough to adapt their services to changing needs. The European Commission welcomes further discussions on the Competence Centers, with the support of KDT JU, the European institution that runs the European programme that will implement the Competence Centres, to facilitate their establishment and operation, foster collaboration among stakeholders, and facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices.

ANNEX

Snapshots from the Live Brainstorming Sessions

These are snapshots of the inputs received (only SMEs and Large Enterprises) that were used to compile this report. This represents just a subset of the inputs received from the audience.

SEMICONDUCTOR CENTRES FOR COMPETENCE

 ALLPROS eu
Watch the new video
and follow our channel

 allpros.eu
 [@allpros_eu](https://twitter.com/allpros_eu)
 [company/allpros-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/allpros-eu)